

**GOD, MORAL AGENTS, AND ETHICS: IF GOD IS TRANSCENDENT,
ATEMPORAL, AND IMPASSIBLE, HOW CAN HE RELATE TO AND INSPIRE THE
MORAL AGENTS WHO ARE FINITE, TEMPORAL, AND IMPERFECT?**

by

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Introduction

Many of the world religions, including Judaism, Christianity, and Islam, believe in the omnipotent, omnibenevolent, and omniscient God.¹ God is absolutely independent, self-sufficient, immutable,² transcendent, and impassible.³ In other words, he is timelessly eternal and outside of space because he brought time, space, and flux into existence. He is unchanging in his being, perfections, purposes, and promises. However, he is immanently present in the creation.⁴ He sustains the creatures through his providence. The religious thinkers and philosophers wrestled with the question of how a transcendent and immutable God could be truly immanent. Numerous explanations are given in the history of philosophy and religion. However, a methodological imbalance of treatment of these aspects was observed.⁵ In this article, the evangelical model that balances the aspects of God's transcendence and immanence and implication for ethics will be explored.

How does a transcendent, atemporal, and impassible God relate to and inspire the moral agents who are finite, temporal, and imperfect? Though God is timelessly eternal and absolutely immutable, he chooses to be intimately involved in the creation that he made while retaining his perfect attributes. The theological confessions of transcendence, immanence, omnibenevolence, and incarnation serve as a foundation for ethics. The moral agents imitate the perfect good in God in their process of growth. In this article, first, the popular explanations of classical theism, process theism, and Moltmann's relational and passible view will be discussed. Then, the evangelical

¹ Richard Swinburne, *The Coherence of Theism* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2016), 1.

² Wayne A. Grudem, *Systematic Theology: An Introduction to Biblical Doctrine* (Leicester: Inter-Varsity Press, 1994), 158–162.

³ Bruce A. Ware, *God's Greater Glory: The Exalted God of Scripture and the Christian Faith* (Wheaton, IL: Crossway Books, 2004), 136–137, 150.

⁴ Grudem, *Systematic Theology*, 158-162.

⁵ Ware, *God's Greater Glory*, 36.

model will be discussed to explain how the transcendental God relates to and inspires the moral agents. At last, the moral and ethical implications for moral agents will be explained.

Classical Theism

Classical theism is the system of beliefs that affirm that God is the ultimate reality. It asserts that God is independent of everything (*a se*), simple, perfect without components, immaterial, eternal, and without accidents. He is impassible; in other words, he is incapable of suffering. The thought of classical theism was found in the writings of Plato, Neoplatonism, and earlier Christian writings.⁶ The medieval theologians like Thomas Aquinas affirmed the historical teaching of immutability, relying on church fathers and scriptures.⁷ God is self-existing (aseity), and he always existed eternally. Since God does not contain any contingent attributes, he is incapable of suffering an intrinsic change. God is eternal, timeless, and atemporal, without a past or future. Since God is atemporal, he sees everything as present. This view also presents God as omnipresent, i.e., as the one who is present in all space and time but not confined by any of them. It emphasizes his personal nature and perfections of his will, wisdom, power, and goodness. It also asserts the attributes of all knowledge (omniscience) and all power (omnipotence).⁸ The creation of the world is God's transient work and guided by his immanent activity of knowing, willing, and loving.⁹ God relates

⁶ Brian Leftow, "Classical Theism," in *Routledge Encyclopedia of Philosophy*, ed. Edward Craig, vol. 4, (London, England: Routledge, 1998), 98–100.

⁷ Michael J. Dodds, *Unchanging God of Love: Thomas Aquinas and Contemporary Theology on Divine Immutability*, 2nd ed. (Washington, DC: Catholic University of America Press, 2008), 1.

⁸ Leftow, "Classical Theism," 98–100.

⁹ Dodds, *Unchanging God of Love*, 49.

with the creation, yet he is immutable in his perfections.¹⁰ God is not affected by any external cause; therefore, humans cannot affect God emotionally.¹¹

Classical theism maintains both God's transcendence and his immanence, his otherness and his nearness. However, the attribute of transcendence of God was clearly emphasized over his relationality. Since God is timelessly eternal, absolutely immutable, and impassible, he cannot be affected by the creatures in any sense. This view indicates that all of God's reactions, including his love, wrath, grief, and anger, need to be interpreted as anthropomorphic and metaphorical expressions.¹² Therefore, it implies that God is not relational in a true sense. Although classical theists maintain that God is involved in the world, their strong emphasis on transcendence and their concrete terminology undermines the doctrine of immanence.

If God is absolutely transcendental and perfectly impassible, he cannot experience the sufferings of moral beings and moral agents. How could such a supreme being inspire and transform the passible, time-bound, and imperfect moral agents to imitate him in showing love, compassion, and sensibility? Roberto Sirvent identified the incompatibility between the doctrines of impassability of God and *imitatio Dei*.¹³ This fundamental inconsistency in the doctrinal assertions also casts a doubt on the moral and ethical drawings developed by theistic religious ethicists. However, scripture supports transcendence, supremacy, and the exalted higher position of God above and beyond creation (Gen. 1:1, Isa. 40:22, 57:15, Rom. 11:33-36, Job 11:6-7, Job 26:7, and John 1:1) and his immutability in terms of his being, his perfections, purposes, and his

¹⁰ Dodds, *The Unchanging God of Love*, 4.

¹¹ Leftow, "Classical Theism," 98–100.

¹² Dodds, *Unchanging God of Love*, 107, 140.

¹³ Roberto Sirvent, *Embracing Vulnerability: Human and Divine* (Eugene, Oregon: Pickwick Publications, 2014), 1.

promises (Num. 23:19, Psalm 102:25-27, 33:11, Isa. 46:10, Mal. 3:6, and Heb. 13:8). However, scripture also reveals God's relationality with the creatures in a true sense. God created the world (Gen. 1:1), he sustains it (Heb. 1:3), he is present in it (Jer. 23:24, Col. 1:17), and he is intimately involved in the affairs of humans (Isa. 57:15). According to Christian theism, he sent his only begotten Son to redeem the fallen humanity (John 3:16). None of these expressions are arbitrary; rather, they clearly reveal God's immanence. Classical theism undermines the significance of God's relationality. Therefore, it does not maintain a balanced view of God's transcendence and his immanence. Bruce A. Ware analyzed the methodological imbalance of classical theism.¹⁴ Although classical theism is not a heresy by itself, it requires accommodation of the right perspective of God's relationality and further explanation of how he interacts with and inspires the moral agents.

Process Theism

Process theism incorporates the metaphysical ideas of process philosophy into Christian doctrines of God.¹⁵ It argues that genuine existence must involve process and change; therefore, God must be evolving, just like everything in creation. God is augmenting to himself all the experiences in the universe. The philosophers Alfred North Whitehead and Charles Hartshorne suggest that God is fully involved and affected by the temporal processes. Although process theism does not deny God's attributes of eternity, immutability, and impassibility in some respects, it asserts that God is temporal, mutable, and passable in most respects. According to this view, God

¹⁴ Ware, *God's Greater Glory*, 38.

¹⁵ John B Cobb and David Ray Griffin, *Process Theology: An Introductory Exposition* (Philadelphia: Westminster Press, 1976), 41.

is the supreme creative power; however, all the creatures are co-creators and retain creative power in themselves.¹⁶

Process theology outrightly rejects some of the traditional notions and attributes of God. It denies God's authority to judge and his absolute unchangeability, immutability, and impassibility, and his sovereign control and power.¹⁷ It denies the notion of *creatio ex nihilo* (creation out of absolutely nothing).¹⁸ Although process theism affirms that divine power is the most effective power, in reality, it limits it to merely a persuasive power, instead of a controlling power. It implies that God relates to the creation by a continual creative transformation of the existing beings in order to actualize new possibilities.¹⁹ In essence, the God of process theism is a factor in the universe that establishes the possibilities to actualities and lures the universe toward new forms of realizations.²⁰ Cobb explains process theism as follows:

Process thought, with its different understanding of perfection, sees the divine creative activity as based upon responsiveness to the world. Since the very meaning of actuality involves internal relatedness, God as an actuality is essentially related to the world. Since actuality such as such is partially self-creative, future events are not yet determinative, so that even perfect knowledge cannot know the future, and God does not wholly control the world. Any divine creative influence must be persuasive, not coercive.²¹

According to process theology, God does not possess and exercise sovereign authority, control, and power over the creation. God is limited merely to an influencer and responder. In an attempt to emphasize God's relationality philosophically, it undermined the authority of scriptures and negated God's transcendence and his immutability. Process theism at its core not only

¹⁶ Donald Viney, "Process Theism," *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy*, Summer 2020 ed., ed. Edward N. Zalta, accessed April 04, 2021, <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/sum2020/entries/process-theism/>.

¹⁷ Cobb and Griffin, *Process Theology*, 8–9.

¹⁸ Cobb, 65.

¹⁹ Cobb, 29.

²⁰ Cobb, 43,53.

²¹ Cobb, 52–53.

undermines divine attributes, but it also deviates from the orthodox doctrines of the essence of God and his perfections. According to scriptures, God is the supreme creator who created the universe out of nothing (Gen. 1:1). God is the sovereign Lord over creation who decrees and controls everything in space, matter, and time (1 Chr. 29:11, 2 Chr. 20:6, Ps. 135:6, Isa. 46:10, Dan. 4:35); he is not merely an influencer. If classical theism struggled to explain God's immanence, process theism undermined the doctrines of transcendence and omnipotence of God. It presents a God who is merely an influencer, not a creator or ruler. Therefore, process theism cannot be endorsed by evangelical Christians who believe in the traditional doctrines.

Moltmann's Relational and Passible View

Some of the modern theologians opposed the notion of God's immutability and impassibility. They considered the transcendental attributes to be the influence from Greek philosophy. They limit the transcendental existence of God to the future. Jürgen Moltmann sees the essential nature of God in the future; God only encounters man in the future.²² He also rejects a God who cannot suffer. He says, "a God who cannot suffer is poorer than any Man. For a God who is incapable of suffering is a being who cannot be involved."²³

Moltmann's view contradicts the traditional understanding of God's transcendence as articulated in classical theism and evangelicalism. Although scripture teaches about God's plan for the future, it does not teach an open future. God is revealed as the eternal sovereign Lord in the past, present, and future. Futurism not only diminishes God's transcendental attributes, but it also

²² Jürgen Moltmann, *Theology of Hope: On the Ground and the Implications of a Christian Eschatology* (New York: Harper and Row, 1967), 16.

²³ Jürgen Moltmann, *The Crucified God: The Cross of Christ as the Foundation and Criticism of Christian Theology* (New York: Harper and Row, 1974), 222.

questions the very existence of the all-powerful God in the present.²⁴ Classical theism affirms God's involvement in the world and his incarnation without undermining the doctrine of immutability. Similarly, modern evangelicalism supports God's relationality and his empathy towards the suffering world, without negating his transcendental attributes.²⁵

In response to Moltmann's passable God, Thomas G. Weinandy expressed his concern over undermining God's impassibility in modern theology.²⁶ He points out that God is emotionally impassible, i.e., it is not possible for God to experience emotional changes of state due to his interactions with human beings. However, God the Son suffered in his human nature in the incarnation.²⁷ On the other hand, modern evangelical theologians emphasize God's emotions; at the same time, they uphold God's impassibility in his being. God experiences grief and emotions in his transcendental existence, apart from the incarnation of Christ. The attribute of God's love does not necessitate the possibility of injury or loss to his nature.²⁸ This points out to consider the claims of the evangelical model of God's transcendence and immanence to understand the biblical picture of God's perfect attributes and his relational qualities.

Evangelical Model of Modified Classical Theism

Evangelical theologians proposed a model of modified classical theism, in which they balance both God's transcendence and immanence methodologically. Although God is atemporal

²⁴ John M. Frame, *The Doctrine of God. A Theology of Lordship* (Phillipsburg, NJ: P&R Pub, 2002), 574–575.

²⁵ Norman L. Geisler, *Systematic Theology: God/Creation* (Minneapolis: Bethany House, 2002), 123.

²⁶ Thomas G. Weinandy, *Does God Suffer?* (Notre Dame, IN: University of Notre Dame, 2000), 1.

²⁷ Weinandy, 38–39.

²⁸ Frame, *The Doctrine of God*. 612–615.

and eternal, he still dwells in the creation as the omnitemporal and omnipresent God.²⁹ This view upholds both truths—God is nonspatial in himself (*in se*) apart from creation, and he is spatially present everywhere in relation to creation (*in re*) without incongruity. Therefore, God is both “atemporal” in his existence and “omnitemporal” in relation to the creation.³⁰ Some theologians refer to it as the incarnational model of God’s transcendence and immanence.³¹ According to this view, God—who is non-spatial, atemporal, and self-existing—chose to inhabit the universe that he created.³² Ware summarizes this view as follows:

Hence, in becoming omnipresent and omnitemporal, God did not change in any respect who eternally is apart from creation. He only adds, as it were, the qualities of his being also immanently related to his creation, in all of its points of space and in all of its moments of time.³³

The evangelical model affirms the traditional doctrines of transcendence and immutability but gives equal emphasis to the attributes of omnipresence, omnitemporality, and relationality. Millard J. Erickson argued that God’s transcendence of space and time does not prevent him from acting in space and time. God is non-temporal ontologically, but he is influentially present within time.³⁴ Classical theism asserts that God is absolutely independent, immutable, and impassible. Therefore, it implies that God cannot be affected by the creatures in any sense. However, some evangelical theologians suggest that God is immutable in his being and his ethical attributes, but

²⁹ Ware, *God's Greater Glory*, 133–134.

³⁰ Ware, 135–136.

³¹ Ware, *God's Greater Glory*, 136, 150. It is important to clarify the term “incarnational model” in order to avoid misunderstanding of the term. The incarnational model of God’s transcendence and immanence is analogous to Christ’s incarnation in which God the Son took on himself a new human nature. The term “incarnational model” in this paper does not carry the notion that God became immanent after the incarnation, rather, it suggests that God was immanently present immediately after the creation.

³² Ware, 136–137.

³³ Ware, 136–137.

³⁴ Millard J. Erickson, *Christian Theology*, 3rd ed. (Grand Rapids, MI: Baker Academic, 2013), 343.

he is mutable in terms of his relationship with the creatures.³⁵ If God is mutable relationally, then the creatures affect the creator in some sense and relate to him meaningfully. Ware suggests that although God is not affected in his being and in his perfections, as a person, he feels the pain and suffering in the world.³⁶ Therefore, he is not absolutely impassable in this relational sense. Similarly, Frame points out that God does not change “in himself.” He further explains that God is immutable in his being and essential attributes like his power, wisdom, knowledge, and holiness. God is also immutable in his decretive will, covenantal faithfulness, and truth of his revelation.³⁷ Although God has unchangeable atemporal existence, he is also present in our world of time and looks at the creation from within and shares the perspectives of his creatures.³⁸ He argues against the anthropomorphic notion of immanence in classical theism, which denies the real expression of God’s emotions. He points out that God’s temporal presence in the creation is as real as his atemporal presence apart from the creation.³⁹ Frame asserts that God has emotions; it is not possible for God to have intellectual capacity without emotions. He defines “emotion” in God as his evaluation of what happens in history. In this sense, God rejoices in good and grieves over evil in the world. God’s evaluations are always true and appropriate because God is the ultimate evaluator and supreme judge.⁴⁰ Similarly, Geisler affirmed that God has feelings; however, he framed it slightly differently from Frame and Ware. For Geisler, God’s feelings are unchangeable

³⁵ Ware, *God's Greater Glory*, 139–140.

³⁶ Ware, 147.

³⁷ Frame, *The Doctrine of God*, 567–570.

³⁸ Frame, 570.

³⁹ Frame, 571.

⁴⁰ Frame, 611.

because God does not feel in the sense of passion; rather, he feels in the sense of perception. He does not have sentimentality, but he has sensitivity to the events in the world.⁴¹

The evangelical model of God's transcendence and immanence is well attested by the scriptural data. In Genesis 1:1, God was revealed as the one who is outside of space and time and as the one who brought time and space into existence. In the beginning, God created the heavens and earth out of nothing (*ex nihilo*). It implies God's transcendence, his self-existence, and his eternity. When God created a mutable world, he created it as the one who is immutable and eternal. The creation would perish, but God remains without change (Psalm 102:25-27). It also reveals God's immanence as the one who chooses to create the world and relates himself to it and indwells in it as an external person. God created the universe in an order and structure in order to make it as a dwelling place. God is still immutable in his being and perfections, but he became a creator and sustainer; therefore, he became a relational being (outside of the Trinity) in order to fulfill his good purposes. At the epitome of the creation account, he created humankind in his own image to reflect his glory (Gen 1:26, 27).

God was intimately involved in the relationships of humans and acted decisively to fulfill his purposes throughout the history of redemption. God chose his people, called them, rescued them, and established them so that they proclaim his goodness and faithfulness (1 Chr. 17:20-21). God revealed his covenantal name "YHWH" to Moses (Ex. 3:14). This name suggests God's absolute independence from creation and distinctiveness from creatures and other gods. This is also a covenantal name by which he relates himself to the covenant people. God, being the Lord of creation and controller, chooses a people and nation for himself to reveal his glory, majesty, and supremacy. There is no changeability in his being, morality, and his attributes; rather, there is a

⁴¹ Geisler, *Systematic Theology*, 123.

clear argument for God's intentionality to associate with his people who are in a particular space and time (Ex. 6:7). The scripture portion Isaiah 57:15 beautifully captures God's transcendence and immanence, and it keeps them tied.

For thus says the One who is high and lifted up, who inhabits eternity, whose name is Holy: "I dwell in the high and holy place, and also with him who is of a contrite and lowly spirit, to revive the spirit of the lowly, and to revive the heart of the contrite."⁴²

God is timelessly eternal, highly exalted, supremely holy, and independent from the rest of the creation. However, he dwells with the humble to revive their spirit. Since God is unchanging in terms of his decrees, promises, and purposes, he remains as a faithful God (Mal. 3:6). God is gracious and merciful, and he abounds in his steadfast love to his covenant people (Ps. 145:8). Since God is the Lord of heaven and earth, he does not dwell in temples built by men. He is not dependent on humans for anything. We are dependent on him and live in him. He gives life to the creation and sustains everything (Acts 17:22-27). The incarnation of Jesus Christ is the profound expression of God's transcendence and immanence. In the beginning, God the Son was co-equal and co-eternal with the Father (John 1:1). Therefore, he was timeless, eternal, and outside the created space. However, he chooses to be the Immanuel, as the one who dwelt among his people (John 1:14). The timeless, spaceless, and self-existent God entered into the world as man. God the Son added to himself a human nature and lived a perfect human life. However, we should avoid the notion that immanence and relation with creation began with incarnation. Instead, God was immanent immediately after the creation and omnitemporal in the creation. The evangelical model represents the biblical picture of God's transcendence and immanence and serves as a helpful and viable model.

⁴² Isaiah 57:15 (ESV).

Implications for Ethics

In the twentieth century, many philosophers argued that ethics are not grounded in the assertions about God. The religious beliefs cannot be the axioms for moral and ethical frameworks. The conceptions about God cannot be the basis for affirming what is good and what is evil.⁴³ Instead, philosophers argued for a virtue-based moral philosophy in which love is the focal point.⁴⁴ The criticism about the usage of religious doctrines in formulating ethics was acknowledged by religious thinkers.⁴⁵ Others questioned the doctrines of immutability and impassibility. If God is absolutely independent, atemporal, and impassible, he cannot understand the sufferings of moral beings. How does an all-powerful, all-knowledgeable, all-good. God allows evil and suffering in the world? The conception of a good God is rationally incoherent with the reality of evil in the world.⁴⁶ Sirvent argued that the doctrine of divine impassability is an obstacle for imitating God.⁴⁷

Many religious philosophers and theologians responded to criticism and argued that religion serves as a foundation for ethics.⁴⁸ From a theistic perspective, God is the source of moral accountability and ethical guidance.⁴⁹ God is the supreme, infinite, and transcendent good; other 'goods' in the world are merely a resemblance of his perfect goodness.⁵⁰ The free will argument

⁴³ Robert Merrihew Adams, *Finite and Infinite Goods: A Framework for Ethics* (New York: Oxford University Press, 1999), 3.

⁴⁴ Iris Murdoch, *The Sovereignty of Good* (London: Routledge, 2001), 45.

⁴⁵ Adams, *Finite and Infinite Goods*, 3.

⁴⁶ Eleonore Stump, *Wandering in Darkness: Narrative and the Problem of Suffering* (New York: Oxford University Press, 2010), 3.

⁴⁷ Sirvent, *Embracing Vulnerability*, 1.

⁴⁸ Adams, *Finite and Infinite Goods*, 4.

⁴⁹ Swinburne, *The Coherence of Theism*, 1.

⁵⁰ Adams, *Finite and Infinite Goods*, 7.

suggests that God is good in granting free will to humans, yet humans choose evil over good, resulting in moral evil in the world. Hence, moral evil in the actual world does not contradict God's goodness and his power.⁵¹ William E. Mann argues that love and covenant relationships are possible between the partners of unequal status.⁵² Despite God's status as the ultimate, supreme, and transcendent being, he is still capable of relating to humans and inspiring them to imitate his attributes of love, compassion, and truthfulness. Similarly, the orthodox teachings suggest that the passibility of humans is considered as perfectibility⁵³ as believers are in the process of change. The intellect of humans is impassible as long as it interacts with the ultimate higher intellect, i.e., God.⁵⁴ In this life, the love in the human beings is the reflection of God's love and his perfect goodness.⁵⁵ In the next life, humans achieve a state of unchangeable perfection and ultimate good after the goodness of God.⁵⁶ Though humans as finite beings cannot relate to an infinite God, they are still capable of imitating his moral perfections with the hope that they grow towards the perfection. Richard Swinburne stresses that moral agents are obligated to obey the commands of the benefactor of life.⁵⁷ In this sense, humans are bound to follow the ethical standards of God, which are morally good. Though humans as moral agents undergo sufferings and pain, God redeems

⁵¹ Alvin Plantinga, *God, Freedom, and Evil* (Grand Rapids, MI: Eerdmans, 1977), 30, 49, 63.

⁵² Mann, *God, Modality, and Morality*, 2.

⁵³ Dodds, *Unchanging God of Love*, 12.

⁵⁴ Dodds, *The Unchanging God of Love*, 7.

⁵⁵ Dodds, *Unchanging God of Love*, 223.

⁵⁶ Dodds, *Unchanging God of Love*, 13.

⁵⁷ Richard Swinburne, "Perfectly Good and a Source of Moral Obligation," *The Coherence of Theism*, 2nd ed. (Oxford: Online Ed, Oxford Academic, June 23, 2016), accessed on December 11, 2025, <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780198779698.003.0011>

them, and it contributes to their good.⁵⁸ Christian ethics, with its emphasis on personal relationships, serves as a strong foundation for moral philosophy and ethics.⁵⁹

Conclusion

God is considered as the one who is beyond space, matter, and time and also as a personal God who is present within the boundaries of creation to comfort the people. Christian philosophers and theologians struggled to balance God's transcendental attributes and his relational capabilities. Classical theism asserts that God is absolutely atemporal, immutable, and impassable. If God is absolutely atemporal and beyond the material world, he cannot relate with the people in the time-bound creation. Process theism argued that God is evolving, just like everything in creation. He cannot decree, control, or exercise dominion. Though God's relationality to creatures is emphasized philosophically, it undermined God's transcendence. Similarly, Moltmann rejected the impassibility of God. He argued that if God is incapable of suffering, he is not involved in the true sense. The evangelical model suggests that God is independent, self-sufficient, and transcendent. He brought creation into existence and involved himself in it. God is immutable in his being and his ethical attributes, but he still meaningfully relates with the creatures. The incarnation is the ultimate expression of God's immanent relationship with creation. As the source of all good and perfection, he inspires moral beings to imitate his attributes of love, compassion, and truthfulness.

⁵⁸ Stump, *Wandering in Darkness*, 428.

⁵⁹ Adams, *Finite and Infinite Goods*, 4.

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